

Awareness of and Barriers to Maternal Health Care Services in Ogun State, Nigeria

AUTHOR(S): SOMADE, Eunice Chinwe (RN, RM, RON, RPHN, B.Sc (Ed),
BNSc, M.Sc. Nursing)
AND
ABARIBE, Chidinma Emeka (RN, BNsc, M.Sc. Nursing)

Abstract

Maternal mortality is preventable if women use health facility for delivery. The study therefore examined the awareness of and barriers to maternal health care services in Ogun State, Nigeria. The descriptive survey research design was used in this study. The population of this study consisted of women residing in Ogun State. Multistage sampling procedure was used to select the sample for the study. A total number of one hundred and forty-two respondents were involved in the study. A self-designed questionnaire was used to collect data for the study. The instrument was subjected to face and content validity. A pilot study was carried outside the sampled location to ensure the reliability of the instrument. The reliability coefficient value of 0.83 was gotten as it was adequate to make the instrument reliable for the study. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. The findings of the study revealed that level of awareness of available maternal services is high and women have access to the primary health care centres. The major barriers to utilization of maternal health care service were non availability of modern equipment and cost of maternal health care services. It was recommended among others that Government should encourage women to utilise maternal health care services by providing modern equipment in Primary Health Care (PHC) centres and other hospitals providing maternal health care services.

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About Author

**Author(s): SOMADE, EUNICE CHINWE (RN, RM, RON, RPHN, B.SC (ED), BNSC,
M.SC. NURSING)**

LAGOS UNIVERSITY TEACHING HOSPITAL,
PRIMARY HEALTH CARE,
IFO, OGUN STATE, NIGERIA

AND

ABARIBE, CHIDINMA EMEKA (RN, BNSC, M.SC. NURSING)

DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC HEALTH NURSING,
BABCOCK UNIVERSITY, ILISAN-REMO,
OGUN STATE, NIGERIA

Introduction

Globally, 287,000 mothers die yearly as a result of pregnancy and delivery related causes, mostly from developing countries (Bustreo, Say, Koblinsky & Pullum, 2013). Maternal deaths are preventable if women give birth in a health facility. To reduce maternal deaths, providing skilled attendant at birth, with right to use emergency obstetrical service, is an effective method (Gabrysch & Campbell 2011). Several factors are associated with giving birth in a health facility, these includes mother's education, economic status, location of abode and distance to health facility, care during pregnancy, and perceived quality of service which results into high rate of maternal mortality in Nigeria (Karkee & Binns, 2013).

In 2018, WHO (2019) reported that globally, Africa recorded the highest MMR of 449 per 100000 live births. The use of Maternal health care services (MHCS) remain little in sub-Saharan Africa because women in developing countries do not have access to this services, including Nigeria (Babalola & Fatusi, 2017); where only 58% of pregnant women have attended at least one clinic during pregnancy, 39% of births are attended to by a skilled professional, 35% of deliveries take place in a health facility and 43.7% receive postnatal care (National Demographic Health Survey, 2011).

Maternal Health Care Services are planned services provided to care for the health needs of women during pregnancy (ANC), labour (delivery care), and postnatal care (PNC) or puerperal periods so as to reduce illness and deaths (Gabrysch & Campbell, 2011). Maternal healthcare services are very vital since it ensures that both maternal and child mortalities are prevented.

According to World Health Organization (2019), access to health care services is important particularly at the crucial time of birth so as to ensure that delivery is a pleasurable experience. Access to health services is inadequate and most mothers are poor, uneducated or rural dwellers. With the strong positive association that is evident between level of care obtained during pregnancy and the utilisation of health facility for delivery, antenatal care also stands as a key to indirectly reduce maternal mortality.

The researcher observed that some women were not aware of maternal health care services while some women who were aware tendered excuses acting as hindrances to access the service. Ibekwe and Ajaeagbu (2010) stated that many of these PHC centers are not efficient due to lack of kits, essential supplies, qualified workers and frequent stock out. This may have necessitated the choice of orthodox delivery services by pregnant women. Hence the need to examine awareness of and barriers to maternal health care services.

The study examined the awareness of and barriers to maternal health care services in Ogun State, Nigeria. The study specifically examined:

1. the level of awareness of the available maternal health care services;
2. the barriers to utilisation of maternal health care services;
3. the relationship between parity and the awareness of maternal health care services; and
4. the relationship between the level of education of women and their awareness of maternal health care services.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the level of awareness of the available maternal health care services in Ogun State?
2. What are the barriers to utilisation of maternal health care services in Ogun State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were generated for this study:

1. There is no significant relationship between parity and the awareness of maternal health care services.
2. There is no significant relationship between the level of education of women and their awareness of maternal health care services.

Methodology

The descriptive survey research design was used in this study. The population of this study consisted of women residing in Ogun State. Multistage sampling procedure was used to select the sample for the study. A total number of one hundred and forty two respondents were involved in the study.

A self-designed questionnaire was used to collect data for the study. The instrument consisted of three sections namely Section A, B and C. Section A sought for the respondents socio-demographic data while Section B consisted of items on awareness of maternal health care services and Section C consisted of items on barriers to utilisation of maternal health care services. The instrument was validated by finding the validity and reliability.

To ensure that the instrument is valid, it was subjected to face and content validity. The instrument was subjected to comprehensive screening by experts in Nursing Science. In so doing, all irrelevances and ambiguous items in the instrument were eliminated. A pilot study was carried outside the sampled location to ensure the reliability of the instrument. The internal consistency of the instrument was ensured by subjecting the data collected to a statistical test using Cronbach alpha analysis. It yielded reliability coefficient value of 0.83 as this was adequate to make the instrument reliable for the study.

The questionnaire administered was distributed and then collected for analysis which was done electronically using Statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) 21st edition. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics took care of the research questions while the hypotheses were subjected to inferential statistics and tested using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the level of awareness of the available maternal health care services in Ogun State?

Table 1: Level of awareness of the available maternal health care services

	Frequency	N=142	Percentage
Have you heard of Maternal Health Service before			
No		13	9.2
Yes		129	90.8
What is your initial source of information			
None		14	9.9
Hospital		82	57.7
School		10	7.0
Mass media		10	7.0
Friends/Family		25	17.6
Others		1	.7
Do you know the type of services that are rendered at maternal health care center			
No		23	16.2

Yes	119	83.8
Antenatal Care (ANC)		
Not aware	21	14.8
Slightly Aware	21	14.8
Highly Aware	100	70.4
Delivery Care		
Not aware	24	16.9
Slightly Aware	25	17.6
Highly Aware	93	65.5
Postnatal Care (PNC)		
Not aware	56	39.4
Slightly Aware	30	21.1
Highly Aware	56	39.4
Immunization		
Not aware	19	13.4
Slightly Aware	26	18.3
Highly Aware	97	68.3
Family Planning		
Not aware	31	21.8
Slightly Aware	41	28.9
Highly Aware	70	49.3

Source: Field survey 2020

From the level of awareness of the available maternal health care services in table 1, for have you heard of maternal health service before; the respondents that said yes were 129 (90.8%) while no were 13(9.2%) respondents. Meanwhile for what is your initial source of information; 14(9.9%) had no source of information, 82(57.7%) heard from hospital, 10(7.0%) heard from school, 10(7.0%) heard from mass media, 25(17.6%) heard from Friends/Family while 1(0.7%) respondents heard it from other sources. Moreover for do you know the type of services that are rendered at maternal health care center; the respondent that said no were 23(16.2%) while yes were 119(83.8%).

Whereas for antenatal care (ANC); 21(14.8%) were not aware, 21(14.8%) were slightly aware while 100(70.4%) of the respondents were highly aware. And for delivery care; 24(16.9%) were not aware, 25(17.6%) were slightly aware while 93(65.5%) of the respondents were highly aware. Also for postnatal care (PNC); 56(39.4%) were not aware, 30(21.1%) were slightly aware while 56(39.4%) of the respondents were highly aware. For immunization; 19(13.4%) were not aware, 26(18.3%) were slightly aware while 97(68.3%) of the respondents were highly aware. For family planning; 31(21.8%) were not aware, 41(28.9%) were slightly aware while 70(49.3%) of the respondents were highly aware.

In conclusion, the level of awareness of available maternal health care services is high. While some of them heard it from other sources, majority of them heard it from hospital. As for the services rendered, few were not aware of the postnatal care (PNC) services rendered.

Research Question 2: What are the barriers to utilisation of maternal health care services in Ogun State?

Table 2: Barriers to utilization of maternal health care services

	YES	NO
Do you encounter any form of barrier in making use of maternal health care service	94(66.2%)	48(33.8%)

Barriers to utilization maternal health care	Agree	Disagree
Work attitude of health care providers	66(46.5%)	76(53.5%)
Availability of modern equipment	76(53.5%)	66(46.5%)
Distance of Maternal Health Care Center to home	51(35.9%)	91(64.1%)
Lack of knowledge about the existing service	32(22.5%)	110(77.5%)
Language barrier	45(31.7%)	97(68.3%)
Schedule of maternal health care service	68(47.9%)	74(52.1%)
Lack of money for maternal health care services	50(35.2%)	92(64.8%)
Maternal health care services are free	33(23.2%)	109(76.8%)
Cultural acceptance, husband acceptance of the service rendered	66(46.5%)	76(53.5%)

Source: Field survey 2020

From the barriers to utilization of maternal health care service in table 2, for do you encounter any form of barrier in making use of maternal health care service; the respondent that said yes were 94(66.2%) while 48(33.8%) said no. Meanwhile for work attitude of health care providers; 38(26.8%), strongly agreed, 28(19.0%) agreed, 22(15.5%) disagreed, while 54(38.0%) strongly disagreed. Moreover, for availability of modern equipment; 41(28.9%) strongly agreed, 35(24.6%) agreed, 14(9.9%) disagreed, while 52(36.6%) strongly disagreed.

Also for distance of Maternal Health Care Center to home; 23(16.2%) Strongly agreed, 28(19.7%), agreed 28(19.7%) disagreed while 63(44.4%) strongly disagreed. And for lack of knowledge about the existing service; 13(9.2%) strongly agreed, 19(13.4%) agreed, 33(23.2%) disagreed, while 77(54.2%) strongly disagreed. For language barrier; 21(14.8%) strongly agreed, 24(16.9%) agreed, 33(23.2%) disagreed, while 64(45.1%) strongly disagreed. Moreover, for schedule of maternal health care service; 25(17.6%) strongly agreed, 43(30.3%) agreed, 14(9.9%) disagreed, while 60(42.3%) strongly disagreed. And for lack of money for maternal health care services; 22(15.5%) strongly agreed, 28(19.7%) agreed, 31(21.8%) disagreed, while 61(43.0%) strongly disagreed.

For maternal health care services are free; 18(12.7%) strongly agreed, 15(10.6%) agreed, 25(17.6%) disagreed, while 84(59.2%) strongly disagreed. Whereas for cultural acceptance, husband acceptance of the service rendered; 33(23.2%) strongly agreed, 30(21.1%) agreed, 19(9.2%) disagreed, while 66(46.5%) strongly disagreed. From the above it was revealed that the major barriers to utilization of maternal health care service were: Non availability of modern equipment and cost of maternal health care services.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between parity and the awareness of maternal health care services.

Table 3: Relationship between parity and awareness of maternal health care services

		Awareness
Parity	Pearson Correlation	.017
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.838
	N	142

As shown in the table 3 below, the correlation result between parity and awareness of maternal health care services showed that there is no correlation between parity and awareness of maternal health care services with p-value (0.838) greater than 0.05 and the R-

value calculated (0.017). Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. Hence, there was no significant relationship between parity and the awareness of maternal health care services.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between the level of education of women and their awareness of maternal health care services.

Table 4: Relationship between the level of education of the women and their awareness of maternal health care services

	Educational Level
Pearson Correlation	.281**
Level of Awareness Sig. (2-tailed)	.001
N	142

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

As shown in the table 4 above, the correlation result between level of education of the women and their awareness of maternal health care services shows that there is correlation between level of education of the women and their awareness of maternal health care services with p-value (0.001) less than 0.05 and the R-value calculated (0.281). The null hypothesis was rejected; hence, there was significant relationship between level of education of the women and their awareness of maternal health care services.

Discussion

The result showed that the level of awareness of maternal health services is high and women were highly aware of the available maternal health care services. Majority of the respondents heard it from hospital but few were not aware of the postnatal care (PNC) services rendered. This is similar to study carried out by Fawole (2011) where mothers reported that CHEWs (community health extension worker) and community health agents informed them of the existence of PNC (postnatal care services). However, those who knew about the services did not have adequate information on when post-natal clinics are offered, or for whom. Most mothers assumed that the services rendered at the primary health care center were only for children and for vaccination 45 days after birth. According to World Health Organisation (2019), the postnatal period begins immediately after birth and last six weeks.

The study also showed that the major barriers to utilization of maternal health care service are: Non availability of modern equipment and cost of maternal health care services. According to Ibekwe and Ajaegbu (2010), they suggested that it is due to brain-drain and shortage of health workers, as well as ill-equipped health facilities. Free maternal health care (MHC) by skilled birth attendant (SBA) can only be accessed at the primary healthcare centers (PHC) and secondary health facilities.

The study further revealed that there was no significant relationship between parity and awareness of maternal health care services. According to the study conducted by Raj, Lyons, Skinner and Teijlingen (2012) regarding parity, it is generally argued that those who have more than three living children tend to believe that they are more aware of maternal and reproductive health issues; as such they utilize maternal health services less frequently as compared to those who have had less than three children.

The study however revealed that there was significant relationship between level of education of the women and their awareness of maternal health care services. This is similar to result from the study carried out by Singh (2014) as they found that level of education of respondents and their level of awareness of antenatal care services as well as the utilization of the services was found to be statistically significant. This is quite true as peoples' decisions most of the time are influenced by their level of education as highly educated childbearing

women for example will patronize the best health institution based on their informed minds and perhaps affordability of the service. This is also because the highly educated respondents are likely to earn more to afford even the service cost of the institutions of their choice.

Conclusion

The study concluded that level of awareness of available maternal services is high and women have access to the primary health care centres. The major barriers to utilization of maternal health care service were non availability of modern equipment and cost of maternal health care services. In addition, there was no relationship between parity and awareness of maternal health care services but level of education of the women influenced their awareness of maternal health care services.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Government should encourage women to utilise maternal health care services by providing modern equipment in Primary Health Care (PHC) centres and other hospitals providing maternal health care services.
2. There is need for women to be well educated on utilization of maternal health care services for their antenatal care, delivery, postnatal care, family planning and immunization.
3. The government should reduce the cost of maternal health care to barest minimum and if possible some maternal health care services should be provided free of charge so as to encourage women to utilize maternal health care services.

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